

LINGUISTIC PERFORMANCE OF THE LIBERAL TRUTH IN RUSSIA: FROM THE IMPERIAL LIBERALISM OF THE 19TH CENTURY TO THE PRESIDENTIAL LIBERALISM OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the problems of linguistic performance in modern Russian political reality. The main theme is the theme of presidential liberalism which is connected with imperial liberalism. The linguistic features of presidential liberalism in Modern Russia are depicted in this article.

Rezumat

În articol, se abordează problema performanței linguale din sfera politică rusească contemporană. Tema principală, supusă analizei, este liberalismul prezidențial care vine în acord cu cel imperial și se manifestă la diferite niveluri, inclusiv cel lingual.

The tendencies of linguistic liberalism marked paradigmatic principles of Russia state formation at the end of the first decade of the 21st century which reflects all the consequences of coming from unity philosophy to pluralism philosophy. Unity philosophy accepts the existence of Transcendental Subject which ontologically is the first (Centre, absolute, Substance, the First Principle, The first Beginning, the Truth, Logos, God, "Transcendental Connotation") (J. Derrida) performing the basis of the world and the initial source of pluralism¹. Pluralism philosophy is based on the introducing any object, thing, notion. Being influenced by one and the same thing object (thing, notion) can perform in an opposite way, i.e. the object possesses two opposite possibilities of its behavior.

In postmodernism philosophy ontologically first Transcendental Subject transforms into the presumption of "truth games". In this case truth history is thought as the analysis of "truth games", the games through which the being constitutes itself historically as some experience, i.e. something that can and must be thought.

According to V.E. Kemerov, a problem of the truth emerges only then when man tries to enlarge the borders of the common, involves unknown objects and relations into his experience. The truth defines coincidences of human knowledge with the reality, thus appearing the problem of human being. The truth fulfills some functions: a) being a process points to human thoughts compliance with the reality, b) demonstrates the limit of human means and the perspectives human force changes, c) identifies human adjustment to the level of those problems which if necessary a person should solve.

Appearance of truth problem and the necessity of its decision defines liberalization of state policy that inevitable leads to linguistic liberalism.

In the context of linguistic liberalism we face the change of language policy essence. One gets down from the bundle of ideological principles and practical measures applied in the sphere of language problem solving in the society to the bundle of interpretation procedures relating to the text². According to R. Barthes, text reveals "plurality": "this ideal text consists of many interrelated inner ways not having power over each other; it represents itself the galaxy of connotative things, but not connotations; it has no beginning, it's reversible; it can be penetrated via a lot of routes, none of which is possible to be regarded as the main one; the chain of its mobilized codes gets lost somewhere in the distance, they are "insolvable"(their sense is not subdued to solving principle, so any decision may be occasional); this text can be adopted by any sense systems, though their circle is not closed as the measure of such systems is the infinity of the language itself"³.

In the 19th century the truth or transcendental subject takes the format of plurality or of the text in the imperial ideology of Nikolay's epoch which found its realization in the famous

¹Kosikov, 2008.

²Khalina, 2008.

³Barthes, 1994, p. 14-15.

formula by S.S. Uvarov - "Christianity, Self-governing, Nation" (1832)⁴. This formula demonstrated appealing to the truth as a factor defining the level of those problems which were to be solved by the state of Russian Empire in the second century of New Time of Europe or the new European time - NET.

Net might be seen as a new format A.D. - the epoch which is known as a new era (n.e.). Imperial liberalism is oriented to the establishing of matrix structure which elements are inner differential language forms defined by G.G. Shpet and poetic forms: "They are the essence of the relation to the logical form of a differential provided by a poet with the help of joining ontic [life-practical] meaning of a sintagma to the logical form. They are derivatives of a logical form. So, it turns out that sui genius poetic logics is a kind of an analog to a "logical one" - the studying about inner forms of poetic expression. These forms have their relation to the thing, differentiated one in comparison with the relation of logical forms. That's why here we can speak about the third type of the truth. Poetic truth emerges near material truth and logical one as the compliance of the sintagma to the thing, though fairly existing in reality, being "fantastic" but logically framed"⁵.

The 19th century from BC or the second NET century is the time of imperial liberalism establishment which possesses some characteristic features aiming at the creation of: a) a new Russian text (A.S. Pushkin)⁶; b) a belletristic style to describe every day reality (Russian natural school); c) a new principle to build up a historical event chain (L.N. Tolstoy); d) a conception of text tension (F.M. Dostoevsky); e) a system of Russian literature language styles (the 2nd half of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century); f) a dictionary of live Russian language (V.I. Dal).

In the 21st century, the third NET century all foundations of presidential liberalism are created. They are 1) orientation to discourse psychology ("Message" by President in 2008); 2) revealing paradox graphical spots in history (TV project "Name of Russia"); 3) usage of word game ways to present the spheres of economic theory and "penetration" providing into the structures of world system (economic forums, comments by "the first" and competent people); 4) restoration of semantic space in coherence with initial borders of political argo and youth community methods.

Linguistic liberalism in Russia of the new millennium acquires the shape of interpretation procedure creating some image of a controlled object as a n action system component. Undoubtedly it influences all the communication peculiarities with a language user.

At present time we can point out three environments of linguistic localization where linguistic liberalism takes place: *President's Speech*, *Moderator's Speech (Moderation System)*, *Mode of liberal operation*.

The basic principle to understand *Moderation System*⁷ is the interpretation of this phenomenon as a reservation system, regulation of information flows in the Internet implying a situation when a responsible member of a news group gets a leading role and acts as a moderator to reduce unnecessary volume and prevent undesirable (according to the group rules) traffic moments. *Mode of operation* is a work regime, conditions of information system work; *mode of liberal operation* represents "liberal" work conditions of the information system. Let's stick to the analysis of *Moderation System* in details.

Moderation System is performed by a text reality and text artifacts of the moderators relating to the information state traffic. They take leading positions of "governor of President Administration of the Russian Federation", "President Assistant of the Russian Federation", "First Vice-Premier of the government". In 2008 the functions of President Administration Governor of the Russian Federation were fulfilled by Sergey Naryshkin, the functions of President Assistant were performed by Arkadiy Dvorkovich, the functions of First Vice-

⁴Uspensky, 2002, p. 404.

⁵Shpet, 1980, p. 408.

⁶Gorshkov, 1984.

⁷Kuriyanov, 1993.

Premier of the government were introduced by Igor Shuvalov. In 2007 duties fulfillment of President Assistant was laid upon Vladislav Surkov.

Text activity of moderators includes differentiation or data flow analysis. It is a collecting process of information about division characteristics of a theoretically numerous work of some countable quantity into two parts in the sphere of calculation distribution in scaled environments⁸. The characteristics are coded by elements (marks) of some quantity L . Taking this fact into consideration data flows are not only regarded as data transmission but management, synchronization of parallel processes – partly organized quantities of event as well.

The consequence of events corresponding to interrelated changes of some process (partly organized quantity) is defined as history h ⁹. Operational and logical history takes place in theory and practice programming cases when logical links of management among program actions are established. Remembering information links between moderators the history of program realization takes place.

Process history relies on word, i.e. the consequence of symbols in the alphabet of E events. The nature of their interconnection can be detailed depending on a task. "If this event partly the reaction of one and the same operator, then its appearance can be provoked by management or information transmission. Graphically process history is a graph without borders which peaks correspond to events and arches correspond to the changes among events. Quazi order \rightarrow initiates equivalency relation $I \rightarrow$ on the basis of events quantity that separates the process into uncrossing family histories $p | I \rightarrow$. The meaning of the formula $e \rightarrow e'$ is in the coming from the event e to the event e' with the history h that can be interpreted as "the name" of a change"¹⁰.

Studying the text artifact of information state traffic of the moderator S.E. Naryshkin we can define his functional status in the synchronization of parallel processes in their plurality "Narrative Russia": management logical links (operational and logical history) are set between the actions of a realized program "Foundation of generation NET". As an example of realization of logical management order via the establishment equivalent parallel process relations of every day reality and virtual projecting we can offer the following fragment taken from S.E. Naryshkin's speech at the XIIth St Petersburg International Economic Forum (St Petersburg, 2008):

"Interrelated business expansion is transforming into a force provoking the emergence of down integration. In other words, today there are all means to form a regional unity. First of all these are market principles of national economies functioning and the high degree of their interaction"¹¹.

The character of pointed items creation allows to speak about peculiarities of non-classical esthetics principles appliance in the linguistic constructing of virtual artifacts, i.e. illusional quasi reality. A new esthetic picture of a virtual world without chaos and ideal order is formed¹². According to I.B. Mankovskaya and V.D. Motlevskiy¹³ modern transformations of esthetic perception are connected with its materialization in the shape of a computer not having physical contacts. Materialization of virtual reality is one of the semantic conventions of linguistic liberalism which can be regarded as a searching for an appropriate way between logical thinking and esthetic perception. Semantically loaded becomes that thing that exists but not that is absent. It is achieved due to featured distribution of a virtual artifact. In the following segment we can identify four types of virtual artifact distribution ("materialization" feature providing) or materialization of virtual reality: 1) adj.+noun in possessive case; 2) noun in possessive case (with the prep. "for")+noun in poss.case+adj.+adj.: 3) adj.+noun in poss.case+noun in poss.case+adj.: 4) adj.+noun in poss.case+noun in poss.case. Morphological models of virtual reality materialization are given as a kind of environment scaling for the generation NET.

⁸Toporkov, 2004.

⁹Toporkov, 2004.

¹⁰Toporkov 2004, p. 65.

¹¹Stenography report, 2008, p. 5.

¹²Orlov, 1995.

¹³Virtual reality, 1997.

Morphological models of virtual reality materialization correlate with “indefinite places” which according to R. Ingarden in the semantic space of the text have the main meaningful function¹⁴. Plurality of possibilities marked by indefinite places reveal as R. Ingarden supposes a wide realization of those meaning variants that exist potentially.

The first stage of potential state realization can be related to equally meaningful outsayings. As M.M. Bongardt, I.S. Losev, V.V. Maximov, M.S. Smirnov suggest two outsayings of the natural language describing one and the same quantity of situations can be accepted as equal¹⁵. There is no problem in finding and defining these equally meaningful expressions. However, the situation is different concerning the artificial system. It can be represented by a postmodern sensibility which is responsible for conceptual formation of the results of reflective thinking relating to serious orientations of postmodern culture. They are technology, politics, science, philosophy, architecture, every day reality, style of thinking, communication strategies.

“To speak about expressions which are equal but not identical is possible only in those cases when system actions are divided into internal and external ones”¹⁶. In the system modifying a complicated behavior the internal actions are the actions that define the thinking, i.e. information recycle actions. The internal language system possesses a variety of one meaning. The most significant transformations changing only the form of an expression can be reflected in the external human language – the language of communication. Besides one may speak about equally meaningful expressions but they are not identical for the system. It emerges when some external system reactions to expressions available to being watched and admitted as equally meaningful are identical but it is known that they can differ.

Appealing to the speech made by President Assistant of the Russian Federation A. Dvorkovich we deal with a text forming system “postmodern sensibility”: “World economy is on the edge of recession. It can’t be avoided. We have problems in a banking sector, face demand decrease in raw goods. World crisis influences our fund market. Here it’s important to understand that financial market investments should be regarded as long term investments. It’s not advisable to make unreasonable steps, aim to export the capital. Russian economy is rather developed and capable of getting over a short term stock falling. Another problem is seen in an unclear situation in the corporate sector. Here we mean tax problems of big companies. It should be understood that we are experiencing a changing period. I’m sure the country will take an accurate way and won’t cause global problems in the corporate sector... There is one more important moment. The last international events are not a reason for changing our strategic plans. Isolation from other world is a political dead stop. We are not going to refuse the policy we have appointed”.

Here equally meaningful expressions are “here it’s important to understand” and “it should be understood” in the internal language system fill the places of incomplete indefiniteness such as “our strategic plans”, “the policy we have appointed”. These equally meaningful expressions but not identical are presented in the text artifact by A. Dvorkovich by excluding syntagmas: “it can’t be avoided”, “isolation from other world”, “world crisis influences our fund market”, “not a reason for changing our strategic plans”, “an unclear situation in the corporate sector”, “we are not going to refuse the policy we have appointed”.

These expressions being equally meaningful but no identical represent the essence of post-modern sensibility which shows the world via the prism of some possibility that allows to frame it as a whole metaphysics. The world has a quality of the “reverse apocalypses” phenomenon. In A. Dvorkovich’s speech we find out logical links among management program actions. It creates the basis of operational logical history of “incomplete indefiniteness places” – Narrative Russia.

In the lecture given by V.Y. Surkov (being Manager Assistant of President Administration, President Assistant of the Russian Federation on the 8th of June 2007) in the building of Presidium RAS a new variant of liberalism as a history process is introduced. It relies on word,

¹⁴Art phenomenology, 1996.

¹⁵Bongardt *et alii*, 2006.

¹⁶*ibidem*.

consequence of symbols in the events alphabet (this or that operator's reaction) "our home – home of Sovereign democracy". To analyze the situation it's possible to admit the truth of the author's judgments in this article: "The language of linguistic liberalism is a home for the sovereign democracy which from the point of operational logical history performs a place of "incomplete indefiniteness". From the position of history process it is a quasi order that provokes the appearance of equivalency "sovereign democratic project" on the basis of events plurality". The relation of "sovereign democratic project" is identical to "political structure softening". It realizes in the Russian text space via topological transformations, divides the process of coherence formation of the Russian nationality into uncrossing family histories "Russian coherence in the aspect of topological transformations".

The principle of symbol ordering according to the position taken by V.Y. Surkov lies in matrix structures of history, matrixes of the national way of life, character, life outlook. The symbols to be ordered are holistic, intuitional Russian culture consciousness; determination to a political unity via the power functions centralization; political struggle aims idealization; political institute's personification; romantic, poetic further look; demonstration of intellect independence and state sovereignty. The ways of ordering are a sovereign democracy conception and a new projection of Russian culture on a next history. In the commentary the accent is paid to dynamic unstable environments, i.e. the dynamics of developing systems, a special view of the world that is: a) self-governing development with the help of configured resonance impacts that are topologically correct (the principle of four I, "Name of Russia"); b) viewing potential of chaos allowing to constitute new organization forms (Constitution bills, changes in the work of Federal Committee, Russian-Ukrainian conflicts); c) alternativeness of scenarios to develop a complicated system in the context of a known inertia historical predictability of changes in the complicated system "Russian state" in the places of branching (*Kiev Russia, Moscow Russia, the Romanovs, Katherine II, October Revolution, Russia, President, Patriarch, sovereign democracy, Global Crisis, Constitution, Cathedral*); d) qualitative structural differentiation between the unity and its parts (virtual artifact "Russia" is not identical to the territorial and administrative unity "the Russian Federation"); e) inevitable interference of localization spheres into initial structures (the territorial and administrative formations), seen in the transformations of the energetic potential; f) self-organization that unstable systems are capable of; g) understanding of the world as a hierarchy of environments with a different line.

The new type of dynamics is a bundle of self-organizing processes in the chaotic unstructured environments which is performed in the realization "Building generation NET". It differs the process of information flows regulation in countable variety "Narrative Russia", suggests production of a corresponding notion apparatus that can be seen in I.I. Shuvalov's speeches, First President Assistant of Russian Government.

Devaluation

"We have taken the definition of devaluation. Devaluation is a sharp falling of rouble rate. In this meaning devaluation does not take place".

The lexical term *devaluation* correlates to the Latin word *valeo* "have a meaning, is worth something". It's transformed in the term *devaluation* into the meaning (1) 'national currency fall relating to foreign currency or gold as a consequence of inflation or payment balance deficit of the country'; (2) 'depreciation, meaning loss of something'. The procedure of taking a decision in the text artifact by I.I. Shuvalov is better to interpret as a procedure of semantic destruction of a lexical unit *devaluation*: the variants of the first meaning 'decrease', 'rate' are actual; the variants 'national', 'currency' are transforming into the sign 'rouble'; the second meaning completely and a part of the first variants meaning are out of the sign *devaluation*.

Siberia becomes a part of Russia

"At the present moment those tasks laid upon Russia make us look at this region in a different way. We realize that over the next decades the greatest success will be achieved by those who can combine mineral resources and extracted resources with the intellect product"¹⁷.

¹⁷Shuvalov, 2008.

Appealing to the territorial characteristics of Russia may be obviously classified as a certain type of political and economic orography. Orography itself implies description of ground surface objects and their classification according to their external features regardless their origin. Political and economic orography suggests knowledge of this or that surface resource and the ability to transform senses playing on this surface or “profits” into virtual artifacts. Siberia is a region of extracting resources. The same complex “enlarge” is replaced by the model of a semiotic behavior “extract”.

Follower’s psychology

Bury the psychology of a following country. “Russians copy French people but fifty years later. So one side modernization takes place” (Stendhal).

Analyzing this stable combination the problem of a human deep motivation becomes clear – the question of life sense and view sociology. According to M. Veber human’s behavior is dominated by ideas and world pictures as well created by ideas¹⁸. World pictures defined the ways which interests’ dynamics took to move ahead human actions. The human action *trace* marked by a lexeme “trace” must be coordinated by the semes “force”, “move”, “enlarge”, “increase” and “limit”. Besides synchronic functional realizations in different communicative contexts of the sign *trace* allow to add it another meaning “understand, realize”. The lexical unit *psychology* has three meanings including the meaning “psyche, character peculiarities, soul structure”. So, the set combination “follower’s psychology” can be interpreted as “spiritual structure of a person understanding every day reality connections or a synchronic text-event”.

Energy trap

Get rid of energy swear not allowing to diversify.

The usage of stable combinations *energy trap* and *energy swear* show the language materialization with the help of a rhetoric function: the usage of “poetic” ways takes place. The literature message as J. Dubois states differs in the fact that poetic direction of the text suggests “elimination” of the thing via the word¹⁹. Due to metaboles literature speech concentrates on itself and the relation motivated to objects by them can be significant only in the frames of a certain text artifact. Specific relation to objects lies in the fact that they are presented (a word performs instead of an object) and absent simultaneously (a word doesn’t coincide with an object) in speech.

Insufficient skills

Learn to work in an innovative environment and to use Peter’s the Great experience.

This stable combination in its functional status is identical to the previous one: it’s the very means that devoid the language its utility function transforming it into a poetic language suitable for esthetic consciousness and destroying the denotation.

Determination of the state to domination

“In the innovative society surplus of the state is as dangerous as its lack”²⁰.

The set expression *determination of the state to domination* being interpreted via the expression *surplus of the state and its lack* includes such components of its seme as “slip”, “wealth”, “profit”, “plurality”, “absence”, “need”, “quality”. The result of non-line self-organized processes logics can be the formation of some duets: *plurality of slips, absence of need, wealth of qualities, lack of profit* (metaplasms, additional structures, items of the poetic language) (I); *plurality of absence, need in profit, quality of slip, wealth of need* (oxymoron, items of the poetic language describing virtual artifacts) (II); *quality “profit”, plurality “wealth”, absence (empty plurality) “need”, “slip”* (logical categories characterizing the functioning of bade in-esthetic consciousness in the frames of “sovereign democratic project”).

Instrument

¹⁸Veber, 1990.

¹⁹Dubua, 2006.

²⁰Ivanitskaya 2008, p. 41; Smirnov 2008, p. 7.

“The group being responsible for the preparation and its methodic accompanying of state and municipal workers is an instrument that must fulfill everything mentioned above”.

“Everybody should do his duties. If at the local level municipal authorities can do this business in an appropriate way then it should be introduced for the population perfectly, better than it can be done by regional authorities. So, in this case it is to be either via entitle delegation or we mark them as our own entitles. It is a flexible instrument and should be treated as if you do it constantly. It means that you’ll have a list. We introduce a law in the Parliament, President will sign it and so, this list will be defined forever. It’s a live instrument which we’ll work with”²¹.

The lexical item instrument is a linguistic variety of desmoplasms – ferment groups disrupting organic unities via the breakage carbon-carbonized links and having a great significance in the breathing processes of tissues. On the one hand, such items encourage text artifacts adaptation in the conditions of communication but on the other hand, fulfill the function of joining the text to the language system and further to language consciousness. As a result the process of text artifacts production is becoming identical to the desmolis process, i.e. a process that disrupts a coherent unity of a denotation and a connotation in the live tissue of organic unities of a natural language under the metaterms influence which mark absence/presence of an object.

Thus the conducted analysis of Moderation System components allows to point out the following characteristic features of this environment type where linguistic liberalism locates from a language point: 1) materialization of virtual reality: formation through structurally complicated feature of operational logical history; 2) cultivation of reverse apocalypses relation as a basis of operational logical history through the system of equally meaningful items but not identical to the system “postmodernism” sensibility; 3) history building of a sovereign democracy process or topological transformations of the society into coherence “Russian nation” on the basis of matrix structures regarded as historical places of “incomplete definiteness”; 4) working out of a new logics identical to a new type of dynamics – the logics of non-line processes in chaotically non-structurized environments via creation of a new metaplasma notion apparatus that encourages parallel changes of a creation process of “a unique intellect product” (political history of realization costs in the program “intellect product”).

Imperial liberalism is the third type of the truth modeling the virtual artifact of “self-governing nation based on the maintaining word” (and so the essence of Slovenes operating the word masterfully). In the 21st century it transforms into presidential liberalism appealing to system moderation (controlling, slowing and balancing) of ontic forms that are pure forms of essential and possible material contents.

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²¹Stenogram, 2004.

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